

TO STUDY THE ACTIVITY OF EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT CENTERS

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Annotation: This article deals with important information about studying the activity of emergency management centers. Moreover, historical background of emergency management and definition of the State emergency management office were analyzed.

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Emergency management or disaster management is a science and a system charged with creating the framework within which communities reduce vulnerability to hazards and cope with disasters. Emergency management, despite its name, does not actually focus on the management of emergencies, which can be understood as minor events with limited impacts and are managed through the day-to-day functions of a community. Instead, emergency management focuses on the management of disasters, which are events that produce more impacts than a community can handle on its own[1]. The management of disasters tends to require some combination of activity from individuals and households, organizations, local, and/or higher levels of government. Although many different terminologies exist globally, the activities of emergency management can be generally categorized into preparedness, response, mitigation, and recovery, although other terms such as disaster risk reduction and prevention are also common. The outcome of emergency

management is to prevent disasters and where this is not possible, to reduce their harmful impacts. Emergency planning aims to prevent emergencies from occurring, and failing that, initiates an efficient action plan to mitigate the results and effects of any emergencies. The development of emergency plans is a cyclical process, common to many risk management disciplines, such as business continuity and security risk management, wherein recognition or identification of risks as well as ranking or evaluation of risks are important to prepare. There are a number of guidelines and publications regarding emergency planning, published by professional organizations such as ASIS, National Fire Protection Association (NFPA), and the International Association of Emergency Managers (IAEM).

Cleanup during disaster recovery involves many occupational hazards. Often, these hazards are exacerbated by the conditions of the local environment as a result of the natural disaster. Employers are responsible for minimizing exposure to these hazards and protecting workers when possible, including identification and thorough assessment of potential hazards, application of appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE), and the distribution of other relevant information in order to enable the safe performance of work.

A team of emergency responders performs a training scenario involving anthrax. Emergency management plans and procedures should include the identification of appropriately trained staff members responsible for decision-making when an emergency occurs. Training plans should include internal people, contractors and civil protection partners, and should state the nature and frequency of training and testing. Testing a plan's effectiveness should occur regularly; in instances where several businesses or organisations occupy the same space, joint emergency plans, formally agreed to by all parties, should be put into place. Drills and exercises in preparation for foreseeable hazards are often held, with the participation of the services that will be involved in handling the emergency, and people who will be affected. Drills are held to prepare for the

hazards of fires, tornados, lockdown for protection, earthquakes and others. In the U.S., the Government Emergency Telecommunications Service supports federal, state, local and tribal government personnel, industry and non-governmental organizations during a crisis or emergency by providing emergency access and priority handling for local and long-distance calls over the public switched telephone network[2].

Emergency management was institutionalized in 1979 with the creation of the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA). Five Federal agencies that dealt with many types of emergencies consolidated to form FEMA. Since that time, many State and local organizations have changed the names of their organizations to include the words: emergency management. The name change indicates a change in orientation from specialized preparedness for single or narrowly defined categories of hazards toward an all-hazards approach that includes potential threats to life and property through environmental and technological hazards, and domestic and foreign attacks. This change reflects not a reduction in security, but an increased emphasis on making the nation's emergency management capability responsive to any major emergency[3].

Public health emergencies are often complex, protracted, and can overwhelm public health systems typically staffed and equipped for routine operations. Recent US and international responses to polio eradication (2011–present), the Ebola virus disease outbreak in West Africa (2014–2016), and Zika virus disease in the Americas (2016–2017) required extended field operations and response structures to bring partners together in a coordinated effort. Applying the concepts of emergency management, including the use of Emergency Operation Centers (EOCs) and Incident Management Systems (IMS) can help national and subnational public health systems protect populations impacted by a public health threat[3]. For the United States, the National Response Framework (NRF) outlines the common structures national, state, and local governments use to

respond to natural disasters, public health, medical, and other emergency situations. The NRF includes roles, responsibilities, and legal authorities used by different agencies within the US government during a response and applies to national, state, and local governments. An organization's Emergency Management Program (EMP) comprises both preparedness and response activities. Preparedness activities, such as exercises and training, can help prepare field epidemiologists for response operations. The EMP facilitates efficient, coordinated public health activities for the duration of a response. Most EMPs use a tiered level of activations; in the United States, these generally range from Level 3 (lowest activation level) to Level 1 (highest activation level). This flexibility enables an organization to right-size response operations to meet changing response requirements.

When an emergency situation occurs, employers may be expected to protect workers from all harm resulting from any potential hazard, including physical, chemical, and biological exposure. An employer should provide pre-emergency training and build an emergency action plan. Employers should train their employees annually before an emergency action plan is implemented to inform employees of their responsibilities and/or plan of action during emergency situations. The training program should include the types of emergencies that may occur, the appropriate response, evacuation procedure, warning/reporting procedure, and shutdown procedures. Training requirements are different depending on the size of workplace and workforce, processes used, materials handled, available resources and who will be in charge during an emergency. After the emergency action plan is completed, the employer and employees should review the plan carefully and post it in a public area that is accessible to everyone[5].

To sum up all given facts above, the State emergency management office is responsible for protecting communities and citizens within the State. The State

office carries out statewide emergency management activities, helps coordinate emergency management activities involving more than one community, or assists individual communities when they need help. If any community lacks the resources needed to protect itself or to recover from a disaster, the State may help with money, personnel, or other resources.

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